

SUSTAINABLE RECYCLING OF CIGARETTE BUTTS: PRODUCTION OF RECYCLED PAPER AND HARDBOARD

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Abstract

Cigarette butts (CBs) are among the most littered waste materials globally, contributing significantly to environmental pollution. CBs primarily consist of cellulose acetate, a plastic-based filter wrapped in paper, and contain residual toxic chemicals such as nicotine, tar, and heavy metals. This study explores an innovative recycling process to convert cigarette butts into recycled paper and hardboard, offering an eco-friendly alternative to conventional waste disposal. The methodology involves a series of chemical treatments including ethanol soaking, bleaching, and detergent cleansing to remove contaminants and extract usable fibers. These fibers are then blended with newspaper pulp to produce recycled paper and are then compressed with corn-starch-based adhesives to create hardboard. Results indicate that CBs derived fibers can be successfully repurposed into functional products thus reducing waste and contributing to sustainable waste management. Comparative analysis with existing recycling methods demonstrates the economic and environmental benefits of this approach. Future research will focus on optimizing fiber strength, durability, and industrial scalability for commercial viability.

Keywords: Cigarette Butts, Sustainable Materials, Recycled Paper, Hardboard, Cellulose Acetate, Waste Management, Eco-friendly Products.

Introduction

Cigarette butts (CBs) are a major source of environmental pollution, with over 4.5 trillion butts discarded annually worldwide, contributing significantly to plastic waste accumulation in public spaces, landfills, and water bodies [1]. The slow degradation of cellulose acetate filters makes CBs persist in the environment, and they are known to contain toxic chemicals like nicotine, tar, arsenic, and lead, which can leach into soil and

water, posing risks to ecosystems and human health [2]. Despite the global scale of this issue, current disposal methods, such as landfilling and incineration, fail to address the environmental impact and merely transfer the problem to other areas [3]. This research explores an innovative recycling process to convert CBs into recycled paper and hardboard, contributing to a sustainable waste management framework while offering potential commercial applications for the products derived from this waste.

Previous studies have demonstrated various methods for recycling cigarette butts, including the use of CBs derived cellulose acetate for applications such as road materials [4] and composites [5]. However, few studies have explored the potential of transforming CBs into valuable products such as paper and hardboard. This study introduces an environmentally friendly process for recycling CBs, which has the potential to reduce waste and offer new opportunities for upcycling.

Methodology

Research Approach

This study follows an experimental approach to evaluate the recycling potential of CBs. The methodology is structured to extract, purify, and repurpose CBs fibers, ensuring that the resulting materials are viable for further applications. The process integrates chemical treatments and mechanical processing to produce recycled paper and hardboard, emphasizing material recovery and environmental safety.

Materials

The primary materials used in this study are discarded cigarette butts (CBs), newspaper pulp, and natural binders such as corn starch. These materials were sourced from local/public areas and processed according to standardized methods used in environmental waste management [6].

Collection and Sorting

CBs were collected from designated waste bins and smoking zones.

Figure 1: Collection bins used for collection of CBs

- **Manual Sorting:** Removal of non-filter components such as tobacco remnants and rolling paper.
- **Filter Separation:** Isolation of CBs filters, as they contain the primary recyclable material cellulose acetate fibers.

- **Preliminary Rinsing:** Washing with tap water to remove surface level contaminants before chemical treatment.

Chemical Treatment

To remove harmful residues and prepare the fibers for reuse, a multi-step chemical treatment process was employed. First, the CBs filters were soaked in a mild alkaline solution to break down nicotine and other contaminants, as suggested in previous studies on CBs recycling [8]. The filters were then treated with 10% hydrogen peroxide solution for further purification and then bleached with acetic acid, followed by thorough washing to eliminate residual chemicals [9]. After treatment, the fibers were dried and ready for integration into the recycling process.

Figure 2: Flowchart of the chemical treatment process for CBs filters

Production of Recycled Paper and Hardboard

The purified CBs fibers were mixed with newspaper pulp to improve paper strength and flexibility, following established methods in the paper recycling industry [10]. The mixture was then spread on screens, pressed, and air-dried to form recycled paper sheets. This process was designed to produce high-quality, durable paper that could serve as a sustainable alternative to conventional paper.

Figure 3: Flowchart of recycled paper production.

Figure 4: Recycled paper production process.

Hardboard Formation

For the production of hardboard, the treated CBs fibers were combined with corn starch-based adhesives. The mixture was compressed under controlled pressure to form hardboard sheets/engineered wood products [11]. This method ensures that the resulting hardboard is durable, water-resistant, and suitable for various practical applications, including furniture and construction materials.

Figure 5: Flowchart of hardboard production

Results and Discussion

Observations on Recycled Paper

The recycled paper produced from CBs fibers was flexible and could be folded without breaking. When exposed to water, the paper absorbed moisture but retained its structure after drying. Layering multiple sheets improved the overall strength and thickness of the paper. These findings are consistent with studies that have explored the potential of cellulose acetate in paper production [12].

Figure 6: Recycled paper from CB filters.

Observations on Hardboard

The hardboard made from CBs derived fibers exhibited strong bonding and stability even under pressure. When exposed to moisture, the structure remained intact, demonstrating the effectiveness of the corn starch-based adhesive in creating water-resistant materials. These results align with previous research on the use of plant-based adhesives in engineered wood products [13].

Figure 7: Recycled hardboard from CBs filters.

Microscopy Analysis

To assess fiber integrity and bonding strength, microscopic analysis was performed on a sample of the hardboard. After soaking the sample in distilled water for 10 minutes with a LABOMED Oil Immersion light microscope was used to observe the structure. The fibers retained their integrity, even after exposure to water, which suggests that the recycling process does not significantly compromise the material's strength.

Figure 8: Microscopic view (40x) of hardboard fibers after water exposure, showing intact bonding.

Comparative Analysis

This recycling process presents a more sustainable alternative to traditional methods of CBs disposal, such as landfilling or incineration. Compared to these methods, the production of recycled paper and hardboard offers not only environmental benefits such as reduced waste and lower emissions but also provide economic advantages by creating usable products from what would otherwise be discarded [14].

Conclusion

This study successfully demonstrates the feasibility of recycling cigarette butts into functional products such as paper and hardboard. The results showed that CBs derived fibers, after undergoing chemical treatment, can be integrated into valuable materials with strong mechanical properties.

The findings contribute to the ongoing research on sustainable waste management and material science, offering a potential solution to the growing problem of cigarette butt pollution. Future research should focus on optimizing the recycling process to improve fiber strength and explore larger-scale production methods to ensure commercial viability.

Figure 9: Recycled Hardboard: Wall Clock Base & Table Top.

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